

Chromatographic analysis of benzylidenemalononitrile analogues of 2-chlorobenzylidenemalononitrile

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Manuscript received 6 May 2003, revised 17 October 2003, accepted 3 May 2004

The riot control agent 2-chlorobenzylidenemalononitrile (CS) and its *ortho* and *para* substituted benzylidenemalononitrile (BMN) analogues were synthesised and characterized by spectroscopic techniques (IR, NMR and mass spectrometry). These compounds were also analysed using thin layer chromatography (TLC), high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and gas chromatography (GC). The chromatographic identification parameters such as retardation factor, capacity factor and retention indices were related to the hydrophobicity of synthesised BMN. Since hydrophobicity is an important determinant of the irritancy, the study thus provides a suitable measure for estimating the potential use of the derivatives of CS as tear gas compounds for riot control.

Benzylidenemalononitriles [BMNs] are the chief products of the condensation of substituted benzaldehydes with malonitrile^{1,2}. Derivatives of benzylidenemalononitriles have important applications in various areas of chemistry. BMN derivatives which incorporate bis-(2-chloroethyl) amino groups, a (bis-chloromethyl)pyrrolidine substituent or phenylazopyrimidine residue have been used for chemotherapeutic treatment of cancer³. Other substituted BMN compounds are used as pesticides, fungicides and insecticides⁴. The interest which has been shown in this group of compounds was largely due to use of 2-chlorobenzylidenemalononitrile [CS] as a riot control agent¹. CS causes irritation of eyes, nose, respiratory tract with the consequent production of profuse tears and mucus. It is, therefore, also termed as an irritant or tear gas compound⁵.

It has been reported⁶ that the sensory irritancy of compounds such as 2-chloro BMN viz. CS increases by increasing the hydrophobicity of the molecule. Hydrophobicity of an organic compound does have a direct bearing on many pharmacological properties⁶. In the case of irritants, hydrophobicity may be responsible for absorption through the skin of the individual and therefore, higher hydrophobicity of a chemical may reduce its bioavailability. On the other hand, optimum lipophilicity may be essential for the chemical to reach the appropriate receptor in the humans to elicit irritancy. Since both the effects are not synergistic, a balance has to be struck in the extent of hydrophobicity for compounds to be effective.

In the present work, we synthesised a series of substi-

tuted benzylidenemalononitriles by the condensation of various substituted benzaldehydes with malononitriles in cyclohexane in the presence of piperidine, and determined their hydrophobicity by using chromatographic methods such as TLC, GC and HPLC.

The hydrophobicity in a homologous series was also estimated by determining the retention indices (RI) on columns of different polarities. In the present work, temperature programmed retention indices were determined on non-polar BP-1 (dimethyl polysiloxane) and moderately polar BP-10 [86% cyano propylphenyl dimethyl poly-siloxane] columns.

An attempt was also made to correlate the hydrophobicity of these compounds with their chromatographic identification parameters such as retardation factor (R_f), capacity factor (K) and retention index (RI) etc., so as to estimate their potential use as riot control agents.

Methods for detection, identification and quantitative determination of BMNS and their derivatives are required during their production and also for verification of their use for prohibited activities⁷. The availability of identification data on CS and related compounds would facilitate the verification in case of alleged use of these chemicals.

Results and discussion

The *ortho* and *para* substituted BMNS were characterised using IR ($\nu_{\text{CN}} = 2210\text{--}2269$, $\nu_{\text{C=C}} = 1580$ and 1460), NMR δ 7.9–9.0, (1H, s, =CH), 6.6–8.2 (5H, m, Ar) melting points and microanalysis.

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) is a simple and rapid

method for preliminary identification of a compound. Appler and Christman⁸ reported the versatility and utility of this technique to detect and quantify very low concentration of sulphur mustard (a chemical warfare agent) and irritants viz. [2-chloro BMNS (CS), ω -chloroacetophenone (CN) and dibenzoxazepine (CR)] in the normal phase. There are however no reports on the reverse phase TLC (RPTLC) of these compounds.

The relationship between the chemical structures and chromatographic behaviour of chemicals has been discussed in several papers⁹. However the exact determination of hydrophobic forces was difficult owing to their complexity. Mayer¹⁰ and Hemmi and Overton *et al.*¹¹ used an indirect approach to determine hydrophobicity. They showed a strong relationship between some biological processes and partition of a compound between an organic phase and water, expressed as the partition coefficient. This is the fraction of a dissolved compound that is transferred to the non-polar phase of equal volumes of immiscible solvent. Fujita¹² introduced a substituent constant π derived from partition coefficients, so that

$$\pi = \log \frac{(K/L)X}{(K/L)H} \quad (1)$$

The partition coefficient is expressed as K/L , where K is the fraction in the non-polar phase and L the fraction in the polar phase; X and H are substituted and unsubstituted molecules with analogous structures respectively.

In the present work, separation, detection and identification of substituted benzylidenemalononitriles was carried out both by normal phase TLC (on silica gel-G) and reverse phase TLC (silica gel-G impregnated with *n*-liquid paraffin). All these compounds were poorly separated by normal phase TLC. RPTLC provided a good separation of homologous series of compounds. It is also observed from Tables 1 and 2 that separation was best on reversed-phase TLC plates when *n*-octanol was used as an impregnant.

Direct determination of partition coefficient is often inaccurate especially for compounds that are only, slightly miscible with the two phases. To overcome this difficulty, Boyce and Miborrow¹³ used chromatographic R_m values defined as :

$$K/L \text{ or } R_M = \log [1/R_f - 1] \quad (2)$$

Analogous to π values ΔR_M ¹⁴ can be defined as

$$\Delta R_M = R_{M(X)} - R_{M(H)} \quad (3)$$

where X and H are substituted and unsubstituted molecules of an analogous series respectively.

Table 1. Normal and reversed-phase thin layer chromatography of *ortho* substituted benzylidenemalonitriles

Sl. no.	R	Normal TLC (benzene)*	Reverse phase TLC* (water + acetone) 70 + 30		
			R_f	R_M	ΔR_M
1.	OH	0.53	0.85	-0.75	-0.65
2.	NO ₂	0.523	0.74	-0.57	-0.47
3.	OCH ₃	0.62	0.68	-0.32	-0.22
4.	CH ₃	0.77	0.50	N.M.	n.m.**
5.	F	0.86	0.59	-0.16	-0.06
6.	Cl	0.83	0.44	0.102	0.020
7.	Br	0.82	0.33	0.30	0.20
8.	2,4-Dichloro	0.84	0.24	0.49	0.39

*Mobile phase.
**Not measured.

Table 2. Normal and reverse phase thin layer chromatography of *para* substituted benzylidenemalonitriles

Sl. no.	R	Normal TLC (benzene)*	Reverse phase TLC* (water + acetone) 70 + 30		
			R_f	R_M	ΔR_M
1.	OH	0.53	0.88	-0.86	-0.76
2.	NO ₂	0.52	0.81	-0.62	-0.52
3.	COOH	-	0.80	-0.60	-0.49
4.	OCH ₃	0.62	0.63	-0.23	-0.23
5.	CH ₃	0.77	0.58	-0.07	-0.03
6.	F	0.86	0.54	-0.14	0.04
7.	H	0.77	0.44	-0.10	NM
8.	Cl	0.83	0.29	0.38	0.28
9.	Br	0.82	0.22	0.53	0.44

*Mobile phase.

The observed values of R_f , R_M and ΔR_M are summarised in Tables 1 and 2 for *ortho* and *para* substituted BMNs. An appreciable change in the R_M values was observed by changing the substituents in the phenyl ring. In both the series, increase in R_f values of parent compound was observed by substitution of *ortho* and *para* positions by electron donating groups like [-OH, -CH₃ and -OCH₃]. These R_f values follow a totally reverse trend as compared to normal phase. In other words, as the hydrophobicity of the molecules in-

creases, the R_f values in the normal phase also increase while in RPTLC R_f values decrease. R_f values in RPTLC decrease when electron withdrawing substituents like [-F, -Br and 2,4-dichloro BMN] are present. In the *ortho* and *para* series, it was observed that hydrophobicity values increase when the substituent is changed from -OH to -Br. It is also observed that the compounds having positive ΔR_m show more hydrophobic nature; for example in *ortho* series OH BMN having (R_M value -0.75) is less hydrophobic and 2,4-dichloro BMN (R_M value 0.24) is most hydrophobic.

A convenient determination of hydrophobicity of compounds is important to study their quantitative structure-activity relationship. The logarithm of the partition coefficient, $\log P_{\text{OCT}}$, of a compound in 1-octanol : water has been widely used to represent hydrophobicity^{15,16}. However, the shake-flask method, generally adopted as standard for the determination of $\log P_{\text{OCT}}$, is difficult in measuring very high or low partitions and causes variance in the results due to impurities, decomposition, poor detectability and emulsion formation. HPLC avoids many of the problems and has the added advantage of being easily amenable to automation. Sabatka *et al.*¹⁷ used reverse phase HPLC to measure the hydrophobicity of a series of biphenyl acid and their precursor. Takegoshi *et al.*¹⁸ determined the capacity factor,

K' of a series of fungicidal *N*-phenyl carbamates by HPLC with octadecylsilane (ODS) as a stationary phase and a mixture of acetonitrile and water as a mobile phase, using eq. (4) given below

$$\log K' = \log (t_R - t_0) / t_0 \quad (4)$$

where t_R and t_0 are the retention times of the compound and the unretained reference compound respectively.

We, adopted the HPLC method to determine the hydrophobicity ($\log P$) of the synthesized BMNS from the intercept of the plot of $\log K'$ versus % of MeOH in the mobile phase. The results are summarised in Table 3. It is seen that $\log P$ values follow almost a similar trend as that followed by R_f and ΔR_M values in RPTLC (refer Tables 1 and 2). Slight deviation may be attributed to the differences in the mobile and stationary phases in RPTLC and RPHPLC.

We have observed in an earlier study¹⁹ that $\log P$ is directly related to the irritancy of the compound. The hydrophobicity and hence $\log P$ in the alkyl benzene increases by substituting the benzene nucleus with electron withdrawing groups. The compounds having moderate $\log P$ values of 0.9 to 2.0 appear to have relatively better irritancy, this may be due to the varying rate of reaction of BMNS with SH group of proteins^{19,20}. It was further observed that the

Table 3. RPHPLC separation of substituted benzylidenemalononitriles column ODS, mobile phase-MeOH : water, detector UV at 254 nm

Compd.	R ₂	R ₁	Mobile phase MeOH + H ₂ O (70+30)			MeOH + H ₂ O (60+40)			MeOH + H ₂ O (50+50)			MeOH + H ₂ O (40+60)			MeOH : H ₂ O (30+70)			
			<i>t_R</i>	<i>k'</i>	log <i>k'</i>	<i>t_R</i>	<i>k'</i>	log <i>k'</i>	<i>t_R</i>	<i>k'</i>	log <i>k'</i>	<i>t_R</i>	<i>k'</i>	log <i>k'</i>	<i>t_R</i>	<i>k'</i>	log <i>k'</i>	log <i>P</i>
1	OH	H	0.60	0.245	-0.6	0.73	0.43	-0.36	0.98	0.92	-0.03	1.66	2.19	0.34	3.49	5.711	0.756	1.95
2	Br	H	0.95	0.93	-0.93	1.46	1.86	0.27	2.90	4.68	0.67	5.87	10.28	1.01	15.17	28.17	1.45	2.5
3	H	OH	0.63	0.28	-0.5	0.74	0.45	-0.34	0.93	0.82	0.086	1.31	1.52	0.18	2.42	3.65	0.562	1.6
4	H	F	0.81	0.65	-0.18	1.08	1.11	0.04	1.78	2.49	0.39	3.2	5.15	0.71	7.01	12.48	1.09	2.15
5	F	H	0.79	0.61	-0.2	1.06	1.07	0.03	1.70	2.33	0.36	3.05	4.86	0.68	6.76	12.0	1.08	2.14
6	H	Br	0.98	1.0	0.0	1.46	1.86	0.269	2.78	4.45	0.64	3.86	10.26	1.01	15.38	28.57	1.45	2.5
7	H	CH ₃	0.87	0.77	-0.1	1.20	1.35	0.13	2.09	3.1	0.49	4.12	6.9	0.84	10.13	18.48	1.266	2.38
8	H	NO ₂	0.87	0.77	-0.1	0.81	0.85	-0.07	1.16	1.27	0.10	1.77	2.4	0.38	3.45	5.63	0.75	1.64
9	Cl	H	0.97	0.97	-0.01	1.44	1.82	0.26	2.79	4.47	0.65	5.86	10.26	1.01	15.16	28.15	1.45	2.64
10	NO ₂	H	0.70	0.42	-0.37	0.89	0.75	-0.12	1.30	1.54	0.18	2.15	3.13	0.49	4.36	7.38	0.868	1.75
11	H	Cl	0.95	0.91	-0.04	1.38	1.72	0.23	2.54	3.8	0.58	5.1	8.8	0.94	12.85	23.71	1.37	2.4
12	Cl	Cl	1.24	1.53	0.18	2.15	3.21	0.50	4.71	8.23	0.91	11.02	20.20	1.3	-	-	-	2.75
13	H	H	0.78	0.59	-0.23	1.03	1.020	0	1.61	2.15	0.33	2.89	4.55	0.66	6.31	11.13	1.04	2.0
14	H	OCH ₃	0.91	0.87	-0.06	1.37	1.68	0.22	2.52	3.94	0.59	5.41	9.4	0.97	14.25	26.46	1.42	2.58
15	OCH ₃	H	0.85	0.73	-0.13	11.9	1.33	0.12	2.09	3.1	0.49	4.37	7.4	0.87	11.14	20.61	1.31	2.4
16	CH ₃	H	0.94	0.91	-0.04	1.42	1.70	8.25	2.69	4.27	0.63	5.88	10.3	1.01	15.4	28.61	1.45	2.6

presence of halogen atom at *ortho* position is an important factor to increase the irritancy; the presence of either methyl or methoxy group at *ortho* position shows less irritancy. This may be due to the steric hindrance of the groups.

An indirect estimate of the hydrophobicity of a compound can also be made using the GC technique^{21,22} using two columns of different polarities. On a polar column the hydrophobic compound is expected to elute earlier as compared to a hydrophilic compound; besides polarity of the compound; other factors such as vapour pressure and hydrogen bonding also influence its retention on a column. The overall effect of these factors is the manifestation in the GC retention indices (RI) determined using *n*-alkanes as standards. The corresponding RI values are shown in the Table 4. It is observed, that the magnitudes of retention indices on polar BP-10 column are higher than those on the nonpolar BP-1 column. The difference in RI (ΔI) on the polar and nonpolar columns is always higher for aromatic than for aliphatic substituent.

Table 4. Temperature programmed retention indices of benzylidenemalononitriles (BMN) on BP-1 and BP-10

Carrier gas : N₂ (1 kg⁻² cm²)

Temp. programming : 40° (1 min), 10°/min to 280° (10 min)

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	RI _{VD}		ΔI
			BP-1	BP-10	
1.	F	H	1415.72	1611.86	196.14
2.	H	H	1459.65	1659.63	199.98
3.	CH ₃	H	1558.95	1791.70	232.75
4.	Cl	H	1582.15	1885.00	302.85
5.	Br	H	1670.79	1740.48	69.69
6.	OCH ₃	H	1716.02	1965.38	249.36
7.	NO ₂	H	1748.44	2133.69	385.25
8.	H	F	1400.88	1704.08	303.20
9.	H	CH ₃	1621.42	1929.66	308.24
10.	H	Cl	1650.75	2046.51	395.76
11.	H	Br	1735.51	1831.22	95.71
12.	H	OCH ₃	1811.30	2086.96	275.66
13.	H	NO ₂	1939.41	2326.32	386.91
14.	H	OH	2746.53	2555.76	190.77

Experimental

Materials :

A series of BMNS were synthesised²³ by the conden-

sation of various substituted benzaldehydes with malononitrile in cyclohexane in the presence of piperidine.

The solvents (methanol, acetonitrile, acetone) used for chromatographic analysis were of analytical grade. The lower *n*-alkanes [C₆-C₈] were purchased from B.D.H. and higher *n*-alkanes [C₉-C₂₄] from Fluka; their GC purity was >99%.

Thin layer chromatography :

The separation of all benzylidenemalononitriles was carried out using reverse phase TLC (RPTLC) on silica gel G impregnated with 0.5% liquid paraffin in hexane. The plates were dried at 30° for 8 h before use. Water-acetone 70 : 30, (v/v) was used as an eluant. Each solvent front was allowed to travel a distance, up to 10 cm. The compounds were detected using iodine vapours. These experiments were carried out in triplicate and the R_f values were calculated from the eq. (5).

$$R_f = \frac{\text{Distance travelled by compound}}{\text{Distance travelled by solvent}} \quad (5)$$

A normal phase separation using silica gel G was also carried out. All the experimental conditions were as described above. The R_m values were calculated as reported¹³. ΔR_m values were calculated¹⁴ with reference to the unsubstituted compound-BMN (R₁ and R₂ = H).

Reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography :

A water model ALC-GPC-244 high performance liquid chromatograph comprising two model 6000A pumps, a U6K injector, a model 660 solvent programmer and UV detector (254 nm) was used. The separation of BMNS was carried out on a μ Bondapak C₁₈ column (Water Assoc., Milford, MA, USA) using methanol-water (30% to 70% methanol) as mobile phase at a constant flow rate of 1 ml/min. The capacity factor (K' value) of each BMN was calculated from the following equation.

$$K' = t_R - t_0 / t_0 \quad (6)$$

where t_R and t₀ are the retention times of the compounds and retained reference compounds respectively. The hydrophobicity (log P) values were calculated from the intercept of the plot of log k vs concentration (%) of methanol used in the mobile phase.

Gas chromatographic analysis :

Shimadzu [Model GC-9A] gas chromatograph equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and a CR3A integrator was used for the determination of retention indices of BMNS on two columns [30m × 0.30 mm × 0.25 μ] of

different polarities namely BP-1 [100% dimethyl polysiloxane] and BP-10 [14% cyanopropyl-phenyl dimethyl polysiloxane].

The column was programmed from an initial temperature of 40° (1 min) at the rate of 10°/min to final temperature of 280° (5 min). The injector and detector temperature was maintained at 230°. Nitrogen was used as a carrier gas at a pressure of 1.25 kg cm⁻² at the inlet. Hydrogen and air were used as fuel gases at the pressures of 0.75 and 0.45 kg cm⁻², respectively.

Determination of retention indices (RI)²¹:

The solution (0.1 µl) of BMNs (10–15 ng) in acetone together with *n*-alkane standard was injected on the GC column. The retention times (accuracy ±0.001 min) were recorded by Shimadzu C-R 3A integrator. An authentic sample of each compound was also injected separately and their retention times were compared with that of the components in the mixture.

The temperature-programmed retention indices also called van den Dool's retention²² indices were calculated from the following formula

$$RI_c = 100n [R_x - R_z/R_{z+n} - R_z] + 100 \quad (7)$$

where R_x is the retention time of the compound of interest; n is the difference in carbon numbers between two alkanes on either side of compound X ; R_z is the retention time of the *n*-alkane; and R_{z+n} is the retention time of succeeding hydrocarbon.

Conclusion :

The separation of BMNS using chromatographic techniques was successfully achieved. The chromatographic parameters such as R_f , ΔR_M , capacity factor (K) and retention indices (RI) were correlated to hydrophobicity ($\log P$) of the compounds. It was found that R_f , R_M and K values are higher for hydrophobic compounds and are in concurrence with $\log P$ values. Although the retention indices by themselves do not give a clear picture of hydrophobicity, yet these can be used for unambiguous identification of the compounds. The hydrophobicity, in turn, helps in estimating the irritancy of the compounds. It was found that the BMN derivatives have almost similar hydrophobicity as the well known riot control agent CS.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Mr. K. Sekhar, Director, Defence Research & Development Establishment, Gwalior

for according permission to publish this study. Thanks are also due to Mr. Tapan K. Das for painstakingly typing the manuscript.

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